

Polymorphism of DNA markers linked to bacterial blight resistance genes in useful rice germplasm

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Bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* is found worldwide and wreaks substantial damage on rice yield. Host-plant resistance has proven to be an effective and economical way of controlling this disease. About 23 resistance genes have been identified (Zhang et al 1998). The genes *xa5*, *xa13*, and *Xa21* together have shown resistance to all known races of the pathogen (Huang et al 1997). Pyramiding of these three genes could be impossible using conventional methods because of their masking effects. The use of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) markers can significantly increase the efficiency of marker-assisted selection (MAS). A germplasm survey for polymorphism will facilitate PCR-based marker-aided transfer of BB resistance genes to elite breeding lines in the future.

Fifty-six lines representing indica, japonica, intermediate, wide compatibility, and specific

compatibility germplasm were surveyed for PCR polymorphism to facilitate the marker-assisted transfer of the three BB resistance genes (*xa5*, *xa13*, and *Xa21*) to elite varieties. Table 1 shows the details of DNA markers linked to the BB resistance genes used in the experiment. Table 2 lists the distribution of alleles of the four marker loci linked to the resistance genes among 56 germplasm samples.

For *xa5*, three alleles were identified among germplasm surveyed with RG 556 primers and PCR products digested with *DraI* and RM 122 microsatellite markers. The allele in IRBB5 was designated as allele 1; 29 lines carry this allele. MAS cannot be used in this group because it possesses an allele similar to that of IRBB5. The marker allele in the susceptible line IRBB4 was designated as allele 2. An additional allele was found in six lines and designated as allele 3. PCR products were not

detected in the four rice lines after many attempts, suggesting that these lines carry a null allele. Similarly, using RM 122, three alleles were detected. Allele 1 was detected in 11 lines, allele 2 in 26, and allele 3 in 15 lines; four lines had no allele.

The majority of the genotypes carry either allele 2 or 3. A PCR polymorphism can be generated between these accessions and IRBB5, thus allowing MAS between these lines. Only two lines, IRBB13 and IRBB60, carry allele 1; others have allele 2. This provided a good opportunity to employ MAS. Most of the crosses between IRBB13 and other lines will develop polymorphism. Chungwongse et al (1993) found two alleles of locus pTA 248: allele 1 in IRBB21 and IRBB60 and allele 2 in susceptible lines IRBB4 and HJ74. A third allele was reported by Huang et al (1997) in a survey of 187 germplasm samples. Among 56 lines tested,

Table 1. Details of PCR markers used and their linkage to BB resistance genes.

Marker	Primer sequence (5'—3')	Enzyme	Linked gene	Distance (cM)	Chromosome no.	Reference
RG 556STS	F TAG CTG CTG CCG TGCTGT GC R AAT ATT TCA GTG TGC ATC TC	<i>DraI</i>	<i>xa5</i>	1.7	5	Yoshimura et al (1995)
RM 122	F GAG TCG ATG TAA TGT CAT CAG TGC R GAA GGA GGT ATC GCT TTG TTG GAC	—	<i>xa5</i>	0.4	5	Blair and McCouch (1997)
RG 136STS	F TCC CAG AAA GCT ACT ACA GC R GCA GACTCC AGT TTG ACT TC	<i>HindIII</i>	<i>xa13</i>	5.5	8	Zhang et al (1996)
pTA 248*	F AGC CGC GGA AGG GTG GTT CCC GA R AGA CGC GGT AAT CGA AAG ATG AAA	—	<i>Xa21</i>	0-1	11	Ronald et al (1992)

*Primer sequences are from Chungwongse et al (1993).

Table 2. Polymorphism of DNA markers linked to the BB resistance genes in 56 rice germplasm samples.

Variety	Source ^a	Group ^b	Allele assignment			
			<i>xa5</i> (RG 556)	<i>xa5</i> (RM 122)	<i>xa13</i> (RG 136)	<i>Xa21</i> (pTA 248)
Dee-geo-woo-gen	SCAU	Indica	3	2	2	3
Guang luai 4	SCAU	Indica	3	2	2	3
Aijiao nante	SCAU	Indica	–	–	–	–
Zhai ye queing 8	SCAU	Indica	3	2	2	2
IRBB21	IRRI	Indica	2	2	2	1
Sheng you 2 hao	SCAU	Indica	3	2	2	3
Shen nong 265	SCAU	Japonica	1	2	2	2
IR5598-1	IRRI	Japonica	1	2	2	3
Taichung 65	SCAU	Japonica	1	3	2	3
Dai bai mang	SCAU	Japonica	1	3	2	3
Zi pe han dao	SCAU	Japonica	1	3	2	3
Nong ken 58	SCAU	Japonica	1	3	2	3
GI 1353	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	2	2	2
Hua jing xian 74	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	1	2	2
G02428	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	3	2	3
CPSL 017	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	2	2	3
Dular	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	–	–	2	2
Hao gelao	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	2	2	2
GI 165	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	3	2	3
G2123	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	3	2	3
G2410	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	3	3	2	2
G2417	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	2	2	2
G2615	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	1	2	3
G3004	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	1	2	2
Guang lu ai	SCAU	Indica	1	1	2	3
Cong lu	SCAU	Indica	1	1	2	2
Aijiao nante	SCAU	Indica	1	1	2	2
Zhai ye queing	SCAU	Indica	–	–	2	2
Calotoc	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	1	2	2
Ketan Nangka	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	1	1	2	2
N29	SCAU	Inter	1	1	2	2
Ji dao	SCAU	Indica	2	2	2	2
Nulsuriwai	SCAU	Inter	–	–	2	3
Karang serang 55	SCAU	Inter	2	3	2	3
Mahao 12	SCAU	Inter	2	3	2	3
Haogeo lao 1	SCAU	Indica	2	3	2	3
2595-1	SCAU	Indica	2	3	2	2
2595-2	SCAU	Indica	2	3	2	2
Huan jing xian 55	SCAU	Indica,W & SCV	3	3	2	3
Zhen shan 97	SCAU	Indica	2	3	2	2
Mangu	SCAU	Indica	2	2	2	2
Zai yen qin	SCAU	Indica	2	2	2	2
Zei bu tou	SCAU	Indica	2	2	2	2
Mai xi tou	SCAU	Indica	2	2	2	2
Wan li xian	SCAU	Indica	2	2	2	2
Shen li xian	SCAU	Indica	1	2	2	2
Yun nan bai	SCAU	Indica	1	2	2	2
Hei du 4	SCAU	Indica	1	2	2	2
Aizi pu	SCAU	Indica	2	2	2	3
Hauke zi	SCAU	Indica	1	2	2	2
HI6	SCAU	Indica	1	2	2	3
IRBB4	IRRI	Indica	2	2	2	2
IRBB5	IRRI	Indica	1	1	2	3
IRBB13	IRRI	Indica	2	2	1	3
IRBB60	IRRI	Indica	1	1	1	1
IR24	IRRI	Indica	2	2	2	2

^aSCAU = Rice Germplasm Centre, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou. ^bW & SCV = wide and specific compatibility variety, Inter = intermediate.

23 were reported to carry allele 3, 30 had allele 2, and no allele was reported in one genotype. Allele 1 does not exist among other cultivated lines; this confirmed the hypothesis that the segment carrying *Xa21* was introgressed from the wild species *Oryza longistaminata*. Lines carrying allele 3 can be used in marker-aided breeding programs as they can generate polymorphism between IRBB21 and IRBB60 and these germplasm lines.

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